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ASSESSMENT OF DRUGS IN POST-OPERATIVE PAIN MANAGEMENT

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ABSTRACT

Background and Aims: Pain remains a significant problem following surgical operations and prescribing patterns for post-operative pain have changed little in the last decade. Hence, this study aims to evaluate the drugs used in post-operative pain management. **Study Design, Study Period and Study Site:** A Prospective Observational Study which was conducted at the surgical department by collecting admitted cases of surgery as per the study criteria during the study period of 6 months at Aware Global hospitals L.B. Nagar. **Methodology:** Patients who have undergone surgery were included. The post operative analgesics prescribed were recorded in a specially designed proforma. **Results:** A total of 229 cases were enrolled in the study. The results shown that, majority (39%) of the surgery cases were in the age group of 21-40 years. The majority cases were males (57%) Majority of them were from urban area (63%).The most preferred single entity analgesic is diclofenac which was given to 101 out of 229 (44%) patients. The most preferred combination analgesic is Aceclofenac + Paracetamol which were given to 12(5.2%) patients. The least preferred single entity analgesics were Indomethacin and Codeine Sulphate which were given to 1 (0.4%) patient. **Conclusion:** The goal for postoperative pain management is to reduce or eliminate pain and discomfort with minimal side effects. The study summarizes that multimodal analgesia has to be preferred whenever possible as it reduces pain after surgery and pain assessment scales should be practiced in assessing pain intensity to choose the right analgesic.

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INTRODUCTION

"An unpleasant sensory and emotional experience associated with actual or potential tissue damage, or described in terms of such damage." [1, 2]. Two major mechanisms explain the physiology of pain: Nociceptive (due to stimuli at the nociceptors) and Neuropathic (due to damage of neurons within Central Nervous System) [3]

Postoperative pain is the most undesired consequence of surgery, and if untreated, can lead to delayed recovery and increased hospital stay. [4] Effective post-operative pain control becomes an essential component of the care of the patient who has undergone surgery. Increase in morbidity or mortality is seen due to inadequate pain control. Evidence suggests that surgery decreases the immune system and that this suppression is proportionate to the invasiveness of the surgery. Good analgesia can suppress this deleterious effect.

The benefits of effective postoperative pain management include patient comfort and satisfaction, earlier mobilization, faster recovery with less likelihood of the development of neuropathic pain, a reduced risk of deep vein thrombosis (DVT), fewer pulmonary and cardiac complications, and reduced cost. [5]

Normally, postoperative pain decreases with time and the need for drugs to be given parenterally shall be ceased. The next choice is then a step down to oral opioids and last choice being non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs and acetaminophen. [6] As the experience of pain and opioid effects varies between patients and individuals, so the dosage of opioids is to be titrated for every individual in order to achieve adequate pain control. Analgesics or compounds with less dependency or with high tolerance level should be used if possible. Finally, analgesic therapy and the patient's need for opioid should be evaluated carefully. [7]

Objectives:

The present study will be carried out with the following objectives:

General Objectives: To analyse the prescriptions for drug use in post-operative pain management.

Specific Objectives:

- 1) To assess the demographic data.
- 2) To assess the types of analgesics used.
- 3) To assess the combination of analgesics prescribed.
- 4) To assess the most preferred analgesic and least preferred analgesic.

Rationale of Study:

Pain remains a significant problem following surgical operations and prescribing patterns for post-operative pain have changed little in the last decade. New treatment modalities are still not being used. Results from previous studies revealed that there is scope for improving prescribing habits and minimizing postoperative discomfort and the use of different types of analgesics in combination had significant reduction in the pain scores post-surgery and decrease in duration of hospital stay. Hence, the current study was designed to assess pain scores after surgery and the types of analgesic or combination of analgesic used after surgery. There is a need of massive awareness amongst surgeons about good prescribing habit by following WHO analgesic ladder.

MATERIALS & METHODS:

Source of Data: Case sheets of the post-operative patients.

Method and Collection of Data:

Study Site:

Study will be conducted at Aware Global Hospital LB Nagar, Hyderabad.

Study Duration:

Study will be carried out for a period of 6 months (July to Dec 2016)

Study Design:

"A prospective observational study".

Statistical analysis: All statistical analyses were performed using licensed version of Minitab 17.0. Statistical testing was performed at 0.05 level of significance using two-tailed tests. Analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) model was used to assess the superiority with mean baseline as a covariate; t-test was used for analysis.

Study Criteria:

The study will be carried out by considering following criteria:

Inclusion Criteria:

1. All prescriptions of post-operative patients of both genders.
2. Prescriptions of the post-operative patients willing to participate in the study.

Exclusion Criteria:

1. Prescriptions of the patients not willing to participate in the study.
2. Psychiatric patients who has undergone surgery.
3. Patients excluded were either unconscious, patient with diminished chances of survival, with unstable vital signs.

Case Study Procedure:

Study was conducted at the department of surgery at Aware Global Hospital L.B.NAGAR with prior permission from the head of the department. Patients were enrolled into the study by considering the study criteria. The prescriptions of all the post-operative patients were collected. The required data was collected in a suitably designed data collection form, and the same was analysed as per the objectives of the study. Similarly regarding demographics, choice of analgesic, number of doses (pre and post-operative), diagnosis, allergy and prescribed pre and post analgesics, dose of administration, frequency, route of administration, past medical history and surgical type were collected from patient's clinical history records. Pain scores were summarized as no pain, mild, moderate, severe and worst pain based on Wong-Baker Face Rating Scale.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:**Age:**

The results revealed that maximum number of patients who have undergone surgery fall under the age group of 21-40years followed by 41-60years then followed by 61-80years and the least being 0-20 years.

Table 1: Details of age distribution of the patients.

Age	No of patients	Percentage
0-20	10	4%
21-40	89	39%
41-60	86	38%
61-80	44	19%
Total	229	

*Descriptive Statistics:***Table 2: Details of Descriptive Statistics of Age Distribution**

Variable	T. Count	Mean	SE Mean	St. Dev	Minimum	Q1	Median	Q3	Maximum
AGE	229	44.85	1.10	16.65	4.00	31.00	47.00	57.50	80.00

Figure 1: Descriptive statistics of age group.**Gender distribution:**

Out of 229 patients 130 patients were male and 99 patients were female.

Table 3: Details of Gender distribution of the patients.

GENDER	No of patients	Percentage
Male	130	57%
Female	99	43%
Total	229	

Figure 1: Details of Gender distribution of the patients.

Descriptive Statistics: AGE by Gender

Table 4: Details of Descriptive Statistics of Age by Gender.

Variable	GENDER	T.count	Mean	SE	Mean	StDev	Minimum	Q1	Median	Q3	Maximum
AGE	Female	99	41.96	1.76	17.51	9.00	27.00	40.00	57.00	80.00	80.00
	Male	130	47.05	1.38	15.68	4.00	36.00	49.00	59.00	80.00	80.00

Figure 2: Descriptive statistics of age group by Gender.

Single Entity Analgesic used:

The table below clearly reveals that diclofenac has been used widely in a 101 patients (44.1%) followed by tramadol in 80 patients(34.93%) then followed by aspirin being used in 15 patients (6.5%) followed by ibuprofen in 7 patients(3.06%) followed by aceclofenac in 3 patients(1.3%) and the least preferred being indomethacin which is used in 1 patient(0.43%).

Table 5: Details of single entity analgesia used.

Single entity analgesic	Prescriptions	Percentage
Diclofenac	101	44.1
Aceclofenac	3	1.3
Aspirin	15	6.5
Indomethacin	1	0.43
Ibuprofen	7	3.06
Tramadol	80	34.93

Figure 3: Details of single entity analgesia used.

Preferred Combination Analgesic:

Combination analgesics were prescribed in 30 patients out of 229 patients. The table below indicates that aceclofenac and paracetamol (PCM) was prescribed in 12 patients followed by combination of diclofenac and paracetamol and combination of tramadol and paracetamol was prescribed in 8 patients.

Table 6: Details of combination analgesics used.

Combination Analgesic	No. Of Prescriptions
Aceclofenac + PCM	12
Tramadol+ PCM	8
Diclofenac+ PCM	10

Figure 4: Details of combination analgesics used.

Multimodal analgesia:

From the data we have collected we have seen that pain score in patients post surgery was found to be minimal when multimodal analgesic technique was adopted than with single analgesic technique. Despite evidence showing the benefit of multimodal analgesia, it is still underused.[8] Principles of a multimodal analgesia include control of postoperative pain to allow early mobilization and enteral nutrition, education, and attenuation of the perioperative stress response through the use of regional anaesthetic techniques and a combination of analgesics. Multimodal analgesia is achieved by combining different analgesics that act by various mechanisms at various sites in the nervous system, reducing the incidence of side effects ultimately reducing the doses of the individual.[9,10] Lower incidence of adverse events and effective analgesia has been demonstrated with multimodal analgesia, which shortens hospitalization, improved recovery and function, and reduces healthcare costs.[9].

One-way ANOVA: Pain Score (PS) versus DRUGS

Method

Null hypothesis	:	All means are equal
Alternative hypothesis	:	At least one mean is different
Significance level α	:	0.05 Equal variances were assumed for the analysis.

Factor Information**Table 7: Factor Information of Drugs (PS vs. Drugs).**

Factor	Levels	Values
DRUGS	7	A, B, C, D, E, F, G

Analysis of Variance**Table 8: Details of Analysis of Variance of Drugs vs. PS.**

Source	DF	Adj SS	Adj MS	F-Value	P-Value
Drugs	6	20.31	3.385	1.20	0.306
Error	221	621.95	2.814		
Total	227	642.26			

Means**Table 9: Details of Means of Drugs (A – G) acc to ANOVA.**

Drugs	N	Mean	St.Dev	95% CI
A	7	2.571	0.787	(1.322, 3.821)
B	7	2.000	1.000	(0.750,3.250)
C	23	1.783	1.445	(1.093,2.472)
D	6	3.167	2.041	(1.817,4.516)
E	26	2.692	1.784	(2.044,3.341)
F	61	2.590	1.820	(2.167,3.013)
G	98	2.684	1.660	(2.350,3.018)

* Pooled St.Dev = 1.67757).

Fisher Pairwise Comparisons

Grouping Information Using the Fisher LSD Method and 95% Confidence.

Table 10: Details of Grouping Information Using Fisher Method.

DRUGS	N	Mean	Grouping
D	6	3.167	A B
E	26	2.692	A B
G	98	2.684	A
F	61	2.590	A B
A	7	2.571	A B
B	7	2.000	A B
C	23	1.783	B

Means that do not share a letter are significantly different.

Fisher Individual Tests for Differences of Means

Table 11: Details of Fisher Individual Tests for Difference of Means.

DOL	DOM	SED	95% CI	T-Value	P-Value
B - A	-0.571	0.897	(-2.339, 1.196)	-0.64	0.525
C - A	-0.789	0.724	(-2.216, 0.638)	-1.09	0.277
D - A	0.595	0.933	(-1.244, 2.435)	0.64	0.524
E - A	0.121	0.714	(-1.287, 1.529)	0.17	0.866
F - A	0.019	0.669	(-1.301, 1.338)	0.03	0.978
G - A	0.112	0.656	(-1.181, 1.406)	0.17	0.864
C - B	-0.217	0.724	(-1.645, 1.210)	-0.30	0.764
D - B	1.167	0.933	(-0.673, 3.006)	1.25	0.213
E - B	0.692	0.714	(-0.715, 2.100)	0.97	0.334
F - B	0.590	0.669	(-0.729, 1.909)	0.88	0.379
G - B	0.684	0.656	(-0.610, 1.977)	1.04	0.299
D - C	1.384	0.769	(-0.132, 2.900)	1.80	0.073
E - C	0.910	0.480	(-0.037, 1.856)	1.89	0.059
F - C	0.808	0.410	(-0.001, 1.617)	1.97	0.050
G - C	0.901	0.389	(0.135, 1.667)	2.32	0.021
E - D	-0.474	0.760	(-1.972, 1.023)	-0.62	0.533
F - D	-0.577	0.718	(-1.991, 0.838)	-0.80	0.423
G - D	-0.483	0.706	(-1.873, 0.907)	-0.68	0.494
F - E	-0.102	0.393	(-0.876, 0.672)	-0.26	0.795
G - E	-0.009	0.370	(-0.738, 0.721)	-0.02	0.981
G - F	0.094	0.274	(-0.446, 0.633)	0.34	0.733

(Using CI-56.37%) A:NSAIDS, B:OP, C:PCM, D:NSAIDS+ OP, E:NSAIDS+ PCM,F: OP+ PCM,G:NSAIDS+OP+PCM).

Figure 5: Fischer’s test to compare multimodal analgesia with single analgesia.

Figure 6: Plot representing pain scores versus drugs

Figure 7: Details of residual plots for pain scores.

One-way ANOVA: Pain Score (PS) versus Group

Method

Null hypothesis : All means are equal
 Alternative hypothesis : At least one mean is different
 Significance level α : 0.05
 Equal variances were assumed for the analysis.

Factor Information

Table 12: Factor Information of Group (PS vs. Group).

Factor	Levels	Values
Group	2	1, 2

Analysis of Variance

Table 13: Details of Analysis of Variance of Group vs. PS.

Source	DF	Adj SS	Adj MS	F-Value	P-Value
Group	1	15.07	15.066	5.43	0.021
Error	226	627.19	2.775		
Total	227	642.26			

Means

Table 14: Details of Means of Drugs (A – G) acc to ANOVA.

Group	N	Mean	St.Dev	95% CI
1	37	1.973	1.280	(1.433, 2.513)
2	191	2.670	1.729	(2.433, 2.908)

Pooled StDev = 1.66589.

Tukey Pairwise Comparisons

Grouping Information Using the Tukey Method and 95% Confidence

Table 15: Details of Grouping Information Using Tukey Method.

Group	N	Mean	Grouping
2	191	2.670	A
1	37	1.973	B

*Means that do not share a letter are significantly different.

Tukey Simultaneous Tests for Differences of Means**Table 16: Details of Tukey Simultaneous Tests for Difference of Means.**

DOL	DOM	SED	95% CI	T-Value	Adj. P-Value
2 - 1	0.697	0.299	(0.108, 1.287)	2.33	0.021

* DOL: - Difference of Levels, DOM:- Difference Of Means, SED:- standard error of difference.

* Individual confidence level = 95.00%

Fisher Pairwise Comparisons

Grouping Information Using the Fisher LSD Method and 95% Confidence.

Table 17: Details of Grouping Information Using Fisher LSD Method.

Group	N	Mean	Grouping
2	191	2.670	A
1	37	1.973	B

Means that do not share a letter are significantly different.

*Group-1 contains: A:-NSAID'S,B:-OP , C:-PCM.

Group-2 contains: D:- NSAIDS+ OP, E:- NSAIDS+ PCM, F:- OP+ PCM,G:- NSAIDS+OP+PCM

Fisher Individual Tests for Differences of Means**Table 18: Details of Fisher Individual Tests for Difference of Means.**

DOL	DOM	SED	95% CI	T-Value	Adj. P-Value
2 - 1	0.697	0.299	(0.108, 1.287)	2.33	0.021

*Simultaneous confidence level = 95.00%.

Figure 8: Comparison of Pain Scores between Group-1 and Group-2.

*Group-1 contains: A:-NSAID'S,B:-OP , C:-PCM *Group-2 contains: D:- NSAIDS+ OP, E:- NSAIDS+ PCM, F:- OP+ PCM, G:- NSAIDS+OP+PCM.

Figure 9: Residual Plots for Pain Score between Group1 & Group2.

CONCLUSION

Among the post operative patients, pain remains the most commonly experienced symptom and may vary with different studies and depends on the activities of patients selected. Analgesic use depends upon the severity of pain. In case of mild pain, single analgesics are used and for moderate to severe pain multimodal analgesics.

Statistical analysis revealed that GROUP-1 containing NSAID's, Opioids, and PCM used individually and GROUP-2 containing combination of NSAID'S, Opioids and PCM(multimodal analgesia) showed significant lowering of pain scores in group-2 patients as compared to Group-1 patients.

In conclusion, multimodal pain management therapy should be used whenever possible. Unless contraindicated patients shall receive around the clock regimen of NSAIDS or acetaminophen. Pre-emptive analgesia with such agents as well as regional blocks may be beneficial in ambulatory cases. PCA with morphine or hydromorphone is appropriate for patients undergoing abdominal procedures under general analgesia. If not contraindicated, addition of NSAIDs may lower the narcotic requirement and improve the quality of analgesia. [11]

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ETHICALISSUES

Work that has been described our article does not deal with animal experiments and so Ethical Board/ Ethical Committee approval was not required.

CONFLICTS OF INTRESTS

None

REFERENCES

1. Elvir-Lazo OL, White PF (2010). Postoperative pain management after ambulatory surgery:role of multimodal analgesia. *Anesthesiol Clin*, Vol.28, No.2(Jun), pp.217-24, ISSN 1932-2275.
2. Part III: Pain Terms, A Current List with Definitions and Notes on Usage" (pp 209-214) *Classification of Chronic Pain*, Second Edition, IASP Task Force on Taxonomy
3. Gupta A, Kaur K, Sharma S, Goyal S, Arora S, Murthy RS. CLINICAL ASPECTS OF ACUTE POST-OPERATIVE PAIN MANAGEMENT & ITS ASSESSMENT. *Journal of Advanced Pharmaceutical Technology & Research*. 2010;1(2):97-108.
4. Wels D. Management of Postoperative Pain. *S AfrfamPract* 2012;54(3):S25.
5. Ramsay MAE. Acute postoperative pain management. *Proceedings (Baylor University Medical Center)*. 2000;13(3):244-247.
6. Charlton E. The Management of Postoperative Pain. *Update in Anaesthesia*. *World Anesthesia Online* 1997(7):1-7.
7. Mohammed Reza S, Mohammed EB, Marzieh K, Hassan K, Simin OM. Study of Patient Pain Management After Heart Surgery. *APB* 2013;3(2):373.
8. Australian Prescriber. Post operative Pain management 2013;36(6):202-204.
9. G Ulufer S. Multimodal analgesia for post operative pain management. *Pain management-current issues and opinions* 2012:177-178.
10. White PF, Kehlet H. Improving postoperative pain management: what are the unresolved issues? *Anesthesiology* 2010; 112 (1): 220-5.
11. Garimella V, Cellini C. Postoperative Pain Control. *Clinics in Colon and Rectal Surgery*. 2013;26(3):191-196. doi:10.1055/s-0033-1351138.

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